

Preoperative Anxiety in Surgical Patients: Assessment of Anxiety Levels and the Effectiveness of Medical Staff Interventions

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Introduction

Preoperative anxiety is a common psychological response among patients awaiting surgical intervention and may negatively affect perioperative stability and postoperative recovery. It is associated with increased stress response, hemodynamic changes, and reduced patient satisfaction. The aim of this study was to assess preoperative anxiety levels and evaluate the effectiveness of medical staff interventions.

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional survey of 32 patients was conducted before elective surgery using an online questionnaire (Google Forms). The survey included an assessment of the preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative periods, as well as the perceived effectiveness of communication and psychological support from medical staff. The anxiety level was assessed on a 5-point Likert-like scale (1-no anxiety, 5-high anxiety). Additionally, the clinical case of a patient with SLAP syndrome who underwent surgery under general anesthesia (propofol) was analyzed.

Results

Most patients demonstrated moderate levels of preoperative anxiety. The main concerns included fear of anesthesia, fear of not waking up after anesthesia, fear of intraoperative pain, fear of medical errors, and uncertainty regarding surgical outcomes. Fear of not waking up after anesthesia was reported by 34.3% of patients (3/5), fear of medical errors by 37.1% (5/5), and concern about unfavorable outcomes by 42.9% (5/5). Higher perceived effectiveness of medical staff communication and psychological support was associated with lower levels of anxiety. In the clinical case of a patient with SLAP syndrome, perioperative consultations and standard medical support were provided; however, no significant reduction in anxiety level was observed. The overall anxiety score was 5/10, influenced by previous surgical experience and adaptive coping strategies.

Conclusion

Preoperative anxiety is common among surgical patients and is mainly related to fears associated with anesthesia and surgical outcomes. Effective communication and psychological support from medical staff are associated with reduced anxiety levels and improved patient-centered care.

Keywords

preoperative anxiety, SLAP syndrome, general anesthesia, patient survey, medical staff, psychological support, patient experience